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Banking architecture, late modernism and exposed concrete in Porto Alegre - Brazil

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Resumo

O presente trabalho busca reconhecer e analisar a arquitetura bancária Porto Alegre, influenciada pela prática do concreto aparente e uma modernidade de características já bastante diversificadas; uma produção que se concentrou nos anos setenta, mas atingiu parcialmente as décadas adjacentes. Essa é a arquitetura da estrutura monumentalizada, da experimentação formal, do alto teor artesanal presente. Este último merece destaque pela sua existência dentre dois Brasis, o colonial e o industrial – e de forma curiosa ainda foi capaz de gerar riqueza no detalhe arquitetônico, um desdobramento autóctone próprio de uma modernidade de raízes brasileiras, mas que transcende um certo folclore tropical. O fenômeno da “arquitetura bancária” ocorrido em todo País, cujo epicentro foi São Paulo, contextualiza esta experiência gaúcha e periférica.

Havia naquele período certa dualidade no processo operativo de projeto. Por um lado, existia a notabilidade artística do autor, a autoria da composição particular, o projeto solucionado de modo “artesanal”; por outro, havia os modelos genéricos, quase institucionalizados, de uso corrente e estandardizados para satisfazer a demanda de projetos modernos em escala global. Dois caminhos antagônicos tendo como fatores fundamentais a cultura local de elaboração de projeto e as limitações climáticas, técnicas e econômicas próprias do estado gaúcho. Era o momento, segundo Luis H. H. Luccas, quando se tornava assimétrica a comparação entre arquitetura como concepção individual artesanal ou como projeto coletivo. E a vertente do concreto aparente, dita “brutalista”, em ascensão resgatava a manufatura artesanal dos componentes, seus aspectos primitivos e suas imprecisões, como sinônimo de excepcionalidade, audácia, expressão e novidade. Entretanto, a concepção do concreto enquanto pedra falsa, ou ao menos como um material de envelhecimento rápido e patológico sob condições subtropicais, fatalmente não sobreviveu a intervenções que mascarassem seu sentido.

Enfim, este trabalho busca demonstrar que a Escola Paulista não era a única nem a principal influência dos arquitetos locais. Fica evidente, no entanto, a influência direta de mestres europeus exercida sobre os profissionais locais, destacadamente para a presença subjacente de matrizes miesianas e para a taticidade madura corbusiana. Embora os arquitetos trabalhassem em torno de utopias artísticas, os exemplares mais bem-sucedidos na criação da forma foram justamente os exemplares de composição elementar. Isso contribui em alguma medida com a revisão, o sentido e o prosseguimento da genealogia da arquitetura moderna como um fenômeno ainda a traduzir para os dias de hoje.

Palavras-Chave: Arquitetura Moderna Bancária; Porto Alegre; Anos Setenta.

Abstract

This study aims to recognize and analyze the banking architecture Porto Alegre, a production concentrated in the Seventies which used exposed rough concrete as the main characteristic and late modern features. Brutalist features appeared through monumentalized structures, formal experimentations, and high level of artisanal content applied. This last one deserves special attention due to its existence inside two antagonist Brazils: the colonial and the industrial. Curiously, this apparent contradiction (or duality) was still able to generate high architectural standards, revealing itself as an autochthonous development from Brazilian Modern Architecture, which transcended the general image of a tropical folklore.

There was at that time a certain duality in the operating process of design. On the one hand, the architect searched for and artistic notability through particular compositions, so-called "artisanal" mode. On the other, there were the generic architectural models almost institutionalized, usual and standardized to meet the modern designs demand on a global scale. Two opposing methods dealing with fundamental local factors as the designing culture, and the climate technical and economic limitations typical in South Brazil. According to Luis H. H. Luccas the postwar period marks the asymmetric comparison between architecture as an individual design development or as a collective project. In addition, the rising exposed concrete movement so-called "brutalist" rescued that artisanal manufacture included in the components, with its primitive aspects and its inaccuracies, as a synonym of uniqueness, boldness, expression and novelty. This is a "romantic" aesthetic that countered the synthetic, homogeneous and systematic architectural language developed earlier through international standards. The design of concrete as faux stone, or at least as fast and pathological aging of material under subtropical conditions, fatally did not survive to constructive interventions, which would mask its meaning.

Finally, this paper seeks to show that the so-called "Paulista School" was not the only or the main influence for local architects. Miesian matrices and Corbusien facilities are more feasible. Although the local architects worked around some artistic utopias, the most successful forms used actually elementary compositions. This contributes to the review, the meaning and the continuation of the Brazilian modern architecture as a phenomenon to translate to nowadays.

Keywords: Modern Architecture Bank; Porto Alegre; Seventy years.

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Introduction

This paper aims to recognize and to analyze the late Modern Architecture in Porto Alegre through the so-called “Banking Architecture” phenomenon developed in the Seventies. The topics in this paper are about (i) the bank as an architectural lab in the period, contrasting “free form” figures with elementary solutions –; (ii) the dualities over the creation of a national identity (industry x colony; or tropical weather x climates above the Tropic of Cancer, as examples); and (iii) architectural autochthonous solutions in Porto Alegre: the monumentality was more restrained and the concrete was not so rough in comparison to Sao Paulo, the brutalist epicenter in the period.

The late modernism in Porto Alegre happened around the decades of 1960 and 1970. The so-called “Brutalism” had been seen in the period in Brazil as a pattern to follow, using exposed concrete as a “unifying feature” to group buildings. There were also other characteristics, such as monumental and mastodonical structure (deliberately large spans and few pillars), in-outdoor continuity of spaces, and facades with “empty” or reductionist compositions (inner details with just a few elements).

It is important to emphasize that this paper brings some of the bibliography produced in United States nowadays due to understand the Brazilian context through an external point of view. The case of late modernism in Porto Alegre demonstrates the variety of architectural singularities even within a kind of Brazilian familiarity. This paper aims also to recognize this small divergent image in the whole “Latin America” context, neither Brazilian Architecture as a homogenous group—the “whole” Latin America is not the image of its 21 countries, cultures, and civilizations. The United Nations (UN) actually break down America as two different continents though: The North (and Central) America and the South America. The Office of the Coordinator of Inter-America Affairs (CIAA) actually consolidated the term “Latin America” as a whole gap of knowledge during the Second World War. The millionaire entrepreneur Nelson Rockefeller (1908–1979) was the head of the agency. The American architect Wallace Harrison (1895–1981) was his successor. Although the “Latin America” term can be understandable (and it is usual in United States) as a characterization of such countries, it creates sometimes a kind of misunderstandings, myths, and decontextualized qualities. This paper warns then the placement of completely different cultures in the same group actually creates a quite dangerous space for superficiality in American Modern Architecture historiography.

In his recent work *Latin American modern architecture: ambiguous territories* (New York: Routledge, 2013), Patricio del Real argues that the idea of Latin American architecture was subordinated to early postwar political and cultural anxieties in the United States, and he highlights MoMA as a key stage in the construction of this historical concept, beyond the specifics of any

single exhibition. Del Real considers the multiple and ambiguous images of Latin American modern historiography as the central problem to be worked on. According to the author, the need for a regional construct named “Latin America” permeated postwar modernization before the unfolding of the bi-polar world of the Cold War. Guided by US postwar economic and political strategies, the multiple mirror images and distortions produced at MoMA made modernism in the Americas a contested ground challenged by regional Latin American powers and European cultural centers. Del Real understands that a dominant group of people, and not exposing the cultural diversities in this region created a partial and lopsided history. It is crucial to understand the Brazilian context in the period and its architectural production through such cultural conflict on the construction of a national identity, and usually related with a kind of tropical folklore. Further assumptions relates Modernism with utopic industrializations, European avant-garde ideologies, or political and cultural conflicts. As Reed states, “the aesthetics of modernism come to bear upon these sorts of political actions which are themselves the result of impossible economic choices”.¹

Figure 1 (left): Cocoa farm in Minas Gerais/Brazil in the XIX century. Source: <http://brasilescola.uol.com.br/>

Figure 2: Petrobras P-51 Oil Platform. Source: <http://www.petrobras.com.br/pt/>

These cultural dualities were also transmitted to the Banking Architecture, which worked as an architectural lab in the period. The post 67 period (time of the Brazilian economic miracle) accelerated and spread agencies throughout the country. More than one hundred buildings were built in Porto Alegre. There were two main typologies: the small banking agency and the Bank headquarters. The construction site frequently was formed both with a mixture of industrial components and artisanal solutions adapted directly on the site. Finally, the search for innovation in the design generated technical challenges, which varied in terms of success and failure.

1. Context: Brutalism in Porto Alegre

¹ Justin Read. *Alternative Functions: Oscar Niemeyer and the Poetics of Modernity*. In: *Modernism/modernity*, Volume 12, Number 2. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, April 2005, pp. 253-272 (254).

It is reasonable to say that the first brutalist features in Porto Alegre appear around the transition of the 1950s and 1960s, when architects begin to overvalue the structure of the buildings and to keep the materials on its natural appearance. Brutalism became a cult style, which consolidated in the 1970s. Almost all the governmental buildings and other private sectors (as the banks) adopted Brutalist features an architectural model. As Luccas states, the reinforced concrete gradually started to model sculptural forms:

"The project had a more extensive acceptance of intuition or artistic sensitivity (both lyrical or concretist), rather than a compositional mechanics grounded on rationality; and the execution of buildings entailed expensive processes such as the manufacture of molded elements in disposable wooden frames" ²

According to Luccas, there are two distinct moments in Brutalist architecture in Porto Alegre. The first, 1959–1968, from the Evangelical Center in Porto Alegre to the Brazilian economic "miracle" (1969–1973). It starts with the overvalue under the reinforced concrete structural shape, the excessive exposition of concrete, and prefabrication. The second is the consolidation of Brutalism, post-1968, but with an emphasis on the 70s. Such production emphasize a set of qualities coming from the so-called "Paulista School" as well as local solutions. In both moments, there was also the influence of the Carioca "lyrical" design and European master architects. This is also the architectural scholarship for later banking works.

One previous qualitative and rational design reference is the Public Works & Utilities Services City Department Headquarters (SMOV), by Moacyr Moojen Marques, João José Vallandro, and Leo Ferreira da Silva. This example presents a set of austere solutions against the "mythical sculptural design with no limits made with exposed concrete" ³ (typical in some unrestrained Brutalist segments). Another positive point of SMOV refers to the adaptation of external compositional references. Centralizing vertical circulations and toilets as a typical Miesian axial arrangement, for example, released the building perimeter to a homogeneous facade treatment—disregarding that former modernist special solar shading care towards tropical weathering (Figures 3 and 4)).

SMOV also contains possible developments related to the Corbusian post-War II production. For instance, a superstructure in apparent concrete supported on the outer pillars expanded out of the floor projection in the attic of the building, which creates a peripheral gallery. This tailpiece using dramatic light is clearly a Corbusian influence, according to Luccas in his thesis; as well as the concrete gargoyles and the protective horizontal plan in apparent concrete, something similar to Villa Shodhan (Figures 5 and 6).

² Luccas, Luis Henrique Haas. *Concreto aparente e valorização da estrutura: a influência estética do Brutalismo em Porto Alegre nos anos 60/70*. In: X DOCOMOMO_Brazil Seminar: brutalist connections 1955-75. PUC-PR | Curitiba, 15-18 out., 2013, p.3. (Translated by the author)

³ Luccas, *op.cit.*, 2013, p.19.

Figure 3 (left): Bacardi Building, Mies van der Rohe, 1957. Source: archdaily.mx

Figure 4: Public Works & Utilities Services City Department Headquarters, M. M. Marques; J. J. Vallandro; and L. F. da Silva, 1966 Porto Alegre. Source: Xavier / Mizoguchi, 1987 p.212

Fig 5 (left): SMOV. Source: Xavier / Mizoguchi, 1987 p.212

Fig. 6: Villa Shodhan, by Le Corbusier, 1956, Ahmedabad / India. Photo: Fondation Le Corbusier

In the late 60s, there are some favorable factors for the Brutalist ascendancy. Notably, the apparent concrete, which was gradually gaining notoriety in the previous decade, now assumes the role of protagonist in the composition of modern buildings. Not restricted only to the structure, the concrete is intentionally expanded to innumerable details such as gargoyles, curtain walls, water tanks, ladders, beams, solar shading systems, etc. It also expands the monumentality of the structure, which becomes the essentiality of the building form. All the components -- concrete, clay, glass, wood, and metal – are usually embedded in cross-linked systems derived from a logical process. But especially the concrete, as an ambivalent material, goes beyond the orthogonal grid towards curvilinear schemes (Figures 7 and 8). Luccas tries to explain this behavior as follows:

"At that time, innovation was usually pursued to transform architectural elements, which, in extreme situations, resulted in mutilations thereof. Recovered by Le Corbusier, the traditional gargoyles of Ronchamp (1950) illustrate the situation: they were creatively and continuously modified in his later works. (...) The belief in concrete as an ideal material,

*flexible and malleable, contributed to the freedom with what happened to overcome rules of common sense and to deform building elements"*⁴

Figure 7 (left): Uruguay School, by Ronald Spieker, and Ubirajara Borne, 1971 Porto Alegre. Photo: author
Figure 8: Olympic Center Thermal Pool at UFRGS, by Fernando González, José Albano Volkmer, and Suzana Costa Barboza, 1967 Porto Alegre. Source: Author

As became clear in Luccas dissertation, the influence Corbusian-Carioca architecture, "sensuous" and "extrovert", resulted in a high contrast comparing with the architecture practiced in São Paulo, austere and dramatic. Luccas sought to demonstrate that the difference between architectural results in Porto Alegre and in Rio de Janeiro was due to both dissimilar construction resources and divergent socio-cultural contexts as well. Beyond that, Rio was the Brazilian capital at that time, which created a more "sophisticated" demand for designs in both public and in private sectors. This explains such extroversion and sensuality attributed to the Carioca production in comparison to the containment of Porto Alegre proposals. The construction of Brasília (1960), the new Brazilian capital, illustrates this different political hierarchy and limited resources (Figures 9 and 10).⁵

Finally, the economic crisis lies in the country in 1970s, driven by the 1973oil crisis. It slows down the demand for new construction in Porto Alegre. The Brutalist influence gradually loses force as well. In early 1980s, Brutalism is different in comparison to previous decades (although the exposed concrete had been used for more few years).

⁴ Luccas, *op. cit.*, 2013, p.12 (translated by the author)

⁵ Luis Henrique Haas Luccas. *Arquitetura Moderna Brasileira em Porto Alegre: sob o mito do "gênio artístico nacional"*. Porto Alegre: PROPAR-UFRGS, 2004. (Doctoral dissertation)

Figure 9 (left): Cathedral of Brasilia, by Oscar Niemeyer, 1958. Photo: Marcel Gautherot (c.1960)

Figure 10: Jose Baptista Perreira Planetarium at UFRGS, by F. González and W. Bered, Porto Alegre, 1971.
Source: Author

2. Banking Brutalism in the South

This topic deals directly with the bank buildings produced in Rio Grande do Sul, which somehow expressed or maintained brutalist features. Due to considerable differences in the method of work of the authors, this topic focus on two main aspects: the elementary forms developed for the agencies and headquarters; and the conflict or combination between industrial and artisanal techniques, which created some instigating details.

The examples selected were chosen based on its merits. In general, these buildings present variations over the so-called "great shelter" and "elevated prism under columns"⁶ formal schemes. The typical composition usually contrasts horizontal and vertical planes, emphasize exuberant forms, and proposes facades with minimum components.

2.1. Elementary Forms

Regardless the justifications for establishing new compositional principles, banking elementary forms emerged from usual archetypes, notably volumetries that shaped large roofs with the key concept so-called "monument-building". According to Ströher, this compositional implementation is reliable indeed because "the monumentalized Brutalist characteristic of Paulista School simplifies the complex nature of living and covers an undivided space, which can be played very well throughout the banking program".⁷ This great shelter can be solved by a shell or by one or more upper horizontal planes, for example (Figures 10 and 11).

⁶ Two elementary compositional strategies synthesized by Maria Luiza Adams Sanvitto.

⁷ Ronaldo de Azambuja Ströher. *As Transformações na Tipologia e no Caráter do Prédio Bancário em meados deste século*. Porto Alegre: PROPAR-UFRGS, 1999, p.162. (Master's thesis).

Figures 11 and 12: elementary formal banking schemes used in the period, mainly for the corner lot: the "Shell" (left) and the "horizontal Plan". Source: Author

The so-called "horizontal plan" is one of the most interesting elementary solutions used to create the form. This composition – a horizontal mass under just a few supporting points – provides shading for all the facades and connection between interior and outside of the building. According to Mahfuz, this is a way to create "transparency through deep shadows created by one or more upper horizontal plans".⁸ In this case, the pillars are not positioned straight on the corner, but retreated, which reinforces the horizontality visible on the upper slab in balance. The essence of this formal strategy is similar to one typical Miesian composition, exemplified at the National Gallery in Berlin (1962) (Figure 13 and 14).

Figure 13: CEF Jose do Patrocio, by Jorge Debiagi, Porto Alegre/BR, 1975. Source: Debiagi Collection

Both in Debiagi's banking agency and in the Mies' German pavilion there is a list of similarities, such as glazed facades, cruciform pillars, transferring the compartmentalized part of the program to the subsoil, form-synthesis, horizontality, and economy of sources. The use of horizontal plan

⁸ Mahfuz, Edson. *Transparência e Sombra: o plano horizontal na arquitetura paulista*. Arqutextos: Portal Vitruvius, dez, 2006 (translated by the author)

for shading is also so-called as “Tropical” architecture as well due to the creation of a kind of porch to protect the facades.

Figure 14: National Gallery, Mies van der Rohe, Berlin, 1968. Source: preservationresearch.com

The "great shelter" strategy seemed to be more consistent to lots in the middle of the block. Usually, the supports are located in the longitudinal side edges – under mediatrix - even when another lot is included (reaching then spans with more than 60ft). In such cases, the supports along the side of the lot can be either through a row of pillars, or through an extensive curtains of reinforced concrete (this last one already highlights the building in its urban context). The slab is usually a "superbeam" (sometimes forming one or more porticoes), or a ribbed slab, both with exposed concrete. The front facade is indented and/or glassed. It keeps the concrete as the protagonist of the composition, contrasts lightness and robustness, and maximizes the connection between the interior and the outside of the banking agency.

Figures 15, 16, and 17: Alternative formal schemes for bank building in lots of block half: “superbeam” (left); ribbed slab (center); and portico. Source: Author

The CEF Independencia agency is as an extended variation of such generic and elementary model. The compositional strategy is defined by overlapping planes and ribbed slabs supported on two parallel walls close to the limits of the lot. The form has three essentialities: the monumentalized shelter; the expanded internal hall for public use (ceiling reaching 25ft and amplified primarily by glazing the front facade); and internal sculptural elements (stairs, platforms, and columns).

Figure 18: CEF Independencia banking agency, by Cesar Dorfman, Porto Alegre/BR, 1976. Photo: Xavier; Mizoguchi, 1987, p. 294

The box in the front façade looks like a concrete artifact (half inside and half outside), which reveals the ambivalence between its actual weight and his virtual weightlessness. This effect is maximized through the thin materiality of the glass, but also opposed delicate geometric panels on the sidewalls. This is an artistic appeal to add content to the empty gables surfaces. The furniture, however, dos not have brutalist features. It's not fixed or mixed with walls and other constructive parts (so-called "integral design"). The furniture has simple design coming from a standard catalog. The vegetation interacts with the roughness of the concrete within a naturalistic language. The stony floor keeps the cold aspect. The ceiling enhances the orthogonal lines. Finally, the stylish metallic covering on the core columns contrasts with the rawness of the rough concrete, lying in a parallel scenario.

2.2. Industrial Baroquism

Pilar cruciform and ample space are also shared affinities with São Paulo Brutalist works, such as the famous FAU-USP (V. Artigas C. Cascaldi, 1962), for example. Nevertheless, here the support is again treated as a sculptural form. In the banking architecture, some agencies use the composition with only four equidistant pillars. This it is frequent in the work of Mendes da Rocha, like his own house in Butanta/Sao Paulo (1964). And it is also visible in other cases, such as the Jose Taques Bittencourt (1959), Andre Mendes (1966), and Elsa Berquó, (1967) residences, by Artigas and Cascaldi.

In banking projects, the four equidistant pillars also were seen in Jorge Debiagi works. One example is the CEF Torres banking agency, with surprising sculptural columns (Figures 19 and 20). The slab follows the way in direction to the supports, forming a curve that dilutes on the pillars. This is a combination of artisanal design with the last technologies in reinforced concrete developed in the State. The final result can be understood as a typical Brazilian Brutalism component, coming from the "hegemonic model of the Paulista school, Miesian composition and Corbusien tactility."⁹

⁹ Present in: Ströher, Ronaldo de Azambuja. *op. cit.*, p.144.

Figure 19: CEF Torres pillar. Source: Debiagi Collection

Figure 20: CEF Torres banking agency, by Jorge Debiagi, Porto Alegre/BR, 1977. Source: Debiagi Collection

The lapping process of concrete as a rock has a high interest level in this work. When Max Bill criticized Niemeyer's works calling his technique as "artisanal Barroquism" (almost a redundancy) or "love for the useless", it is complicated to define precisely if it is an apology to elementarity, or a kind of jealousy beyond such incredibly curvilinear and elegant composition through reinforced concrete. Anyway, probably a keyword to analyze it would be "*rocaille*".

The expression *rocaille* (stone) is the act of sculpting masonry, a typical *tekne* came from western culture. Curiously, in Brazil, the greatest manifestation of Baroque – late, indeed – used also wood as confection material. This can be seen as a process of mimesis from the *rocaille* origins. The imaginative and creative "Rococo" can be seen as a combination of the French *rocaille* (stone) and *coquilles* (shell) due to reliance on these objects as decorative motifs.¹⁰ The term may also be a combination of the Italian word "barocco" (an irregularly shaped pearl, possibly the source of the word "baroque") and the French "rocaille" (a popular form of garden or interior ornamentation using shells and pebbles) and may describe the refined and fanciful style that became fashionable in parts of Europe in the 18th century.¹¹ Rococo used to love *shell-like curves*. Debiagi's curvilinear slab has in fact some *modus operandi* that searches in fact for some artistic value. At CEF Torres case, the column design makes sense with the structural efforts (highlighting the elegant connection between support and plan), and not just decorative at all.

¹⁰ Monique Wagner, *From Gaul to De Gaulle: An Outline of French Civilization*. Peter Lang, 2005, pp. 139

¹¹ Marilyn Stokstad, ed. *Art History*. 4th ed. New Jersey: Prentice Hall, 2005.

Although Debiagi uses elementary solutions to solve the banking agency program, the architect tries also to retain his "artistic notability",¹² or a differentiation at least, through peculiar ingredients specific for each work. Detailing is a way to search for originality and also to prevent the possible loss of prestige if all agencies were similar on appearance. This perseverance seems to converge to an argument stated by Luis Espallargas Gimenez, which specifies that the typical brutalist architect "declines and repudiates standard components and impersonal industrial materials just to insist on authorship and inspiration, but repeats stylistic twitches usual in that period and intensively uses the unexplained raw and exposed concrete to feel involved and updated".¹³

Another example of such "creative" treatment can be seen on the "porch" of this agency. Debiagi proposes a modular element - crossbeam in a "J" - and repeats this component configuring a staggering pace, but treats each particular form with its own dimensions (Figures 21 and 22) and exposed concrete. The same can be observed in the treatment of skylights. The dome was repeated, but the fins which control the incidence of light have specific angles and drawings.

Figure 21: View of the entrance CEF Petropolis Agency, Porto Alegre, 1974. Photo: Debiagi collection

Figure 22: Longitudinal Agency CEF Petropolis, Porto Alegre, 1974. Photo: Debiagi collection

In addition to this solar shading, which allows free transparency to the façade and liveliness to the entry (intentionally pulled back), this "porch" keeps the hierarchy between the agency and its context. This structure made with generous dimensions is the main mechanism to check the monumental character of the building. This is a feature that is also consistent with this type of institution. However, the same "J" components retain a plausible negative criticism about its monumental proportion and function, revealing a hard cost and benefit relationship to argue in favor. This can be interpreted as a constructive exaggeration, an economic carelessness that Espallargas defines in his articles as "structural workout" and "tectonic greatness." This last negative criticism over the validity of this "porch" solution (and any gesture of this kind). And this

¹² Term used by Espallargas Luis Gimenez, *op. cit.* 2013, p.2. It is not intended here also make reflections on the artistic function of the architect and investigate its possible existence, but only to point the interest by the authors in particular and sculptural detail.

¹³ Espallargas, Luis. *op.cit.* p.2

Figure 27: Governor's Palace, Le Corbusier, Chandigarh, India, 1952. Source: archdialog.com

3. New Modern Banking Ruins

A final consideration should be mentioned about the current mischaracterization of banking works. Currently, most of them are painted, covered with "Alucobond", and adapted to the new standards against fire. Therefore, it is important to sound a warning to the preservation of this recent architectural production, after fulfilling the primary objective of recognizing and valuing this bank architecture as part of this formal "Brutalist" universe (Figures 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, and 33).

Figures 28 and 29: CEF Moinhos de Vento, By Cesar Dorfman, Porto Alegre, 1973 (original and current status). Source: Xavier; Mizoguchi, 1987, p. 278 (left) and author (right)

Figures 30 and 31: *Itaú Passo d'Areia* agency, Itaúplan, Porto Alegre. Photo (left): Rev. Projeto n° 63, mai/1984, p. 57. Current picture (right): Google Maps

Figures 32 and 33: *Azenha* Banking agency, Itaúplan, Porto Alegre. Photo (left): Rev. Projeto n° 63, mai/1984, p. 56; Current picture (right): autor

Brutalism was used in this paper as a concept used to classify buildings with similar characteristics. If it is actually a matter of collective hallucination as attested by Mahfuz at the X Docomomo Brazil Seminar, then it means that the corruption of the form into a metaphorical meaning can be understandable through how human mind creates and recreates images according the collective reality. As Langdon also states, “the building is poised to renew its original purpose as a symbol of collaboration, testing the resiliency of architecture’s function as an evocative, semiologically charged object of society’s collective memory”¹⁴ And this was the apocalyptic postwar reality. Anyways, it is a fact that these buildings were based on images, such

¹⁴ David Langdon. *United States Embassy in Havana*. Archdaily, Jan. 2015. <http://www.archdaily.com/584114/ad-classics-united-states-embassy-in-havana-harrison-and-abramovitz>

as “Paulista School”, Le Corbusier late works, or other masters mentioned before.¹⁵ But concrete is not a rock (Figure 34).

Figure 34: *Ceci n'est pas une pipe* (The Treachery of Images), by René Magritte, 1928–1929. Source: collections.lacma.org

The exposed concrete can be understood both as a “fake rock”, according to Vitruvius analyzing Roman buildings, and as well as a malleable material capable of multiple forms—and images. This duality is shown in this paper until the final of Modern Movement, when architects tried to use the rough concrete as the generator of the building’s form. Contemporary times however attest its fragility along time. The book *On Weathering: Time of Buildings in Time*, by Mohsen Mostafavi and David Leatherbarrow (Cambridge: MIT Press, 1993) is also a convergent point in the meaning that senescence (the process of getting old with wisdom) is a virtue indeed. It is a fact, indeed, that some architects used consciously the raw concrete to express history. The aging of building is a mature concept of composition. The accumulation of dust, foulness or simply the wear of the material is something that should be predicted in the creation of the architectural design. It is about honesty between the viewer – user – and the limits of the space. Le Corbusier attested that Architecture should create great ruins (Figures 35 and 36).

¹⁵ “Imagination” is a way for criticism in Architecture, and not how is mistakenly used as a corruption of the meaning and the form. Based on: Richard Kearney. *The Wake of Imagination*. New York: Routledge, 1988.

Figures 35 and 36:, *Villa Savoye*, Le Corbusier, 1928-1931. Before restoration of 1985. Source: pinterest.com

Finally, the rising exposed concrete movement so-called "brutalist" rescued that artisanal manufacture included in the components, with its primitive aspects and its inaccuracies, as a synonym of uniqueness, boldness, expression and novelty. This is a "romantic" aesthetic that countered the synthetic, homogeneous and systematic architectural language developed earlier through international standards. The design of concrete as faux stone, or at least as fast and pathological aging of material under subtropical conditions, fatally did not survive to constructive interventions, which would mask its meaning.

To conclude, maybe the restoration of modern buildings is in the word "translation". According to Perez-Gomez, architecture is inextricably linked to politics, and our world is already brutally and falsely unified through technological mediation. In the point of view of the author, Building was a representation of significant action, apart from formal or stylistic considerations. Perez-Gomez also argues that there are two solutions for bringing old concepts to new approaches: "interpretation" and "translation". The author uses the concepts of Rudolf Steiner (1861—1965), which understands that "human communication is essentially translation". Then, translation can never be reduced to a system or mechanism. Apparently, the meaning of philosophical concepts while ethical principles should be transmutable to present days, even if the society and the culture have been changed. Therefore, this is how contemporaneous architects should deal with the banalization of the space: interpreting iconic buildings from the past, understand its composition and translating to new construction in adaptable spaces. In other words, the way is to "provide a sense of orientation and continuity depends on the act of interpreting something that is alien" ¹⁶.

¹⁶ Alberto Perez-Gomez. *Built Upon Love: Architectural Longing after Ethics and Aesthetics*. Cambridge: MIT Press, 2008, p. 140.

Bibliography

Bill, Max. *O arquiteto, a arquitetura, a sociedade*. Habitat 14: A-B, 1954.

Bergdoll, Barry, Carlos E. Comas, Jorge F. Liernur, and Patricio Del Real. *Latin America in construction: architecture 1955-1980*. New York: Museum of Modern Art, 2015.

Del Real, Patricio, and Helen Gyger. *Latin American Modern Architectures: Ambiguous Territories*. New York: Routledge, 2013.

Justin Read. *Alternative Functions: Oscar Niemeyer and the Poetics of Modernity*. In: *Modernism/modernity*, Volume 12, Number 2. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, April 2005, pp. 253-272 (254).

Luccas, Luis Henrique Haas. *Concreto aparente e valorização da estrutura: a influência estética do Brutalismo em Porto Alegre nos anos 60/70*. In: X Seminário DOCOMOMO_Brasil:conexões brutalistas 1955-75. PUC-PR | Curitiba, 15-18 out., 2013.

_____, Luis Henrique Haas. *Arquitetura Moderna Brasileira em Porto Alegre: sob o mito do "gênio artístico nacional"*. Porto Alegre: PROPAR-UFRGS, 2004. (Doctoral dissertation)

Mahfuz, Edson. *Ordem, Estrutura e Perfeição no Trópico: Mies van der Rohe e a arquitetura paulistana na segunda metade do século XX*. *Arquitextos*: Portal Vitruvius, fev. 2005. <<http://www.vitruvius.com.br/revistas/read/arquitextos/05.057/498>>.

_____, Edson da Cunha. *Transparência e Sombra: o plano horizontal na arquitetura paulista*. *Arquitextos*: Portal Vitruvius, dez. 2006.

_____, Edson da Cunha. *An investigation into the nature of the relationship between the parts and the whole in architectural composition*. Ann Arbor, Mich: UMI, 1987.

Mostafavi, Mohsen; and David Leatherbarrow. *"On Weathering: The Life of Buildings in Time"*. Cambridge: MIT Press, 1993.

Perez-Gomez, Alberto. *Built Upon Love: Architectural Longing after Ethics and Aesthetics*. Cambridge: MIT Press, 2008.

Petroli, Marcos Amado. *A avis rara do Arquiteto Jorge Debiagi: Uma Análisesobre a Influência Brutalista em duas de suas Obras Bancárias*. In: X Seminário DOCOMOMO_Brasil:conexões brutalistas 1955-75. PUC-PR | Curitiba, 15-18 out. 2013

Sanvitto, Maria Luiza Adams. *As questões compositivas e o ideário do Brutalismo Paulista*. *ARQtextos*: PROPAR-UFRGS, 2002.

Ströher, Ronaldo de Azambuja. *As Transformações na Tipologia e no Caráter do Prédio Bancário em meados deste século*. Porto Alegre: PROPAR-UFRGS, 1999. (Master's thesis).

Xavier, Alberto. *Depoimento de uma Geração*. São Paulo: ABEA/FVA/Pini, 1987.